

Obstetrical Management of Dystocia Due to Foetal Hydrocephalus in a Non-Descript Doe: A Case Report

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Abstract

A non-descript primiparous doe of complete gestation was presented with a history of progression of labour since six hrs and rupture of the water bag for the past 3 hrs, without progression in parturition. Cause of dystocia was diagnosed as hydrops of cranium accompanied with foetal mal dispositions. Case was managed successfully by reducing the cranium size through trocarization and correction of the foetal posture to ensure the per-vaginal delivery without surgical intervention.

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